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MICROCAPSULE-BASED SELF-HEALING PROTECTIVE COATING USING LINSEED OIL HEALING AGENT

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Self-Healing coating

- Self-healing coatings can be classified into two groups: intrinsic-type and extrinsic-type.
 - In Intrinsic-type coatings, they possess a latent self-healing functionality, so they can heal by the coating matrixes themselves. Intrinsic-type coating system has a major advantage which can heal a repeatable repair, but it has a disadvantage which can only heal very low damage volume.
 - In extrinsic-type self-healing coatings, a healing agent is microencapsulated and the microcapsules are dispersed into the coating matrix. When the microcapsules are ruptured by damage, a healing agent in the microcapsules is released and fills the damaged region. And they are undergone a healing reaction. A microcapsule-based coating system has a major advantage in that it can heal a larger damage volume compared to an intrinsic self-healing system without microcapsules. But the system is one-time healing.
 - My self-healing coating system has advantages of repeatable self-healing of intrinsic-type and a healing of a larger damage volume of extrinsic-type

Self-healing protective coating using linseed oil

Linseed oil

